

POTENTIAL SCREENING METHOD TO IDENTIFY ANTIMICROBIAL DRUGS FOR
SUCCESSFUL TREATMENT OF NAEGLERIA FOWLERI INFECTION

*Ronald Bartzatt

University of Nebraska, Chemistry Department, 6001 Dodge Street, Omaha NE 68182.

*Corresponding Author: Ronald Bartzatt

University of Nebraska, Chemistry Department, 6001 Dodge Street, Omaha NE 68182.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18428415>

How to cite this Article: Ronald Bartzatt. (2026). Potential Screening Method To Identify Antimicrobial Drugs For Successful Treatment of Naegleria Fowleri Infection. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(2), 129–135. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 23/12/2025

Article Revised on 12/01/2026

Article Published on 01/02/2026

ABSTRACT

This study presents a methodology to identify potential antimicrobial drugs for the treatment of *Naegleria fowleri* (*N. fowleri*) infection, which is an amoebic protozoan infection, and in which survival after infection is extremely unlikely. Also known as the “brain-eating amoeba”, this microbe causes primary amebic meningoencephalitis (PAM). This study focuses on a group of antimicrobials that have been found to be effective for the clinical treatment of the deadly *N. fowleri* infection. These drugs are Amphotericin B, miltefosine, fluconazole voriconazole, azithromycin, rifampin, and posaconazole. The molecular properties of these agents was determined and run through extensive statistical analysis to establish a criteria for screening other antimicrobials for the treatment of *N. fowleri* infection. Speed of treatment is vital for surviving *N. fowleri* infection, and this screening methodology is anticipated to increase the efficiency of selecting antimicrobials for successful clinical treatment. The molecular properties of the seven agents that are successful for clinical treatment have been determined and multiple regression analysis of molecular properties of these seven drugs successful and effective in treatment, produced an equation useful for design of similar compounds, based on molecular properties. The 95% confidence interval for the molecular mass of these seven effective agents is 378.3 to 839.1, for Log P is 1.130 to 5.147, for polar surface area is 65.29 A² to 238.23 A², etc. In addition, pattern recognition methodologies Discriminant Analysis, Convex Hulls, and 95% Ellipses are applied to interpret relationships within these multivariate data sets. This methodology has the potential to assist the rapid identification of potentially successful antimicrobials. for the treatment of PAM and specifically *N. fowleri* infections.

KEYWORDS: Primary amebic meningoencephalitis, *Naegleria fowleri*, PAM.

INTRODUCTION

The amoeba *Naegleria fowleri* (*N. fowleri*) will survive in soil, water, and/or in the human central nervous system.^[1] Infection in humans, resulting in PAM (primary amebic meningoencephalitis), is thought to occur through the nasal cavity following exposure, with attachment of the amoeba to the nasal mucosa, then movement along the olfactory nerve, passing through the cribriform plate, then to the olfactory bulbs in the central nervous system.^[1] *N. fowleri* then releases cytolytic molecules, that with active immune response will result in nerve and tissue damage often resulting in death.^[1] Rapid diagnosis and treatment is vital for survival, which is most often within five days of infection. Common symptoms include severe headache, chills, fever, confusion, seizures, cardiac abnormalities, and notably a

tremendous intracranial/cerebral spinal fluid pressure.^[1]

Infection by *N. fowleri* is rare, therefore the implementation of clinical trials for study is unlikely.^[1] Trial and error in clinical treatment, sharing of successful treatment regimen, has resulted in the focus of the following agents as useful for treatment: Amphotericin B, miltefosine, fluconazole voriconazole, azithromycin, rifampin, and posaconazole.^[1,2]

Diagnoses of *N. fowleri* infection is challenging and must be done swiftly for survival.^[2] Symptoms of infection have to be differentiated from other bacterial infections, a process that slows response.^[2] The current recommended treatment can include up to 5 or 6 agents, in which antifungal and antibiotics are combined.^[2] This

infection is fatal in over 98% of the cases.^[2,3] Treatment of PAM, is known to have a significant level of success utilizing among the following antimicrobials: Amphotericin B, miltefosine, fluconazole voriconazole, azithromycin, rifampin, and posaconazole.^[2]

This study will present the analysis of molecular properties of these seven agents successful in the treatment of PAM. A multiple regression analysis of numerical values of these seven agents will enable design of similar agents for similar clinical purpose and in addition allow: 1) Prediction of the dependent variable of molecular mass; 2) Understanding property interrelationships; and 3) Understanding the importance of the independent variables, which are the molecular properties of these clinical pharmaceuticals.^[4] The molecular properties altogether form a multivariate or multidimensional data set in which pattern recognition methods such as Discriminant Analysis, Principal Components Analysis with Convex Hulls and with 95% Ellipses, are used to reduce, recognize, and interpret these large multivariate data sets.^[4] The 95% confidence intervals of the important drug-likeness molecular properties, are determined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Molecular Properties and Molecular Modeling

Determination of the numerical values for molecular properties (i.e. Log P, polar surface area, molecular weight, number of atoms, molecular volume, number of nitrogen, oxygen, amine groups, and hydroxyl groups), for all compounds were determined by Molinspiration Chemical Properties Service, Nova ulica 61, SK-900 26 Slovensky Grob, Slovak Republic (www.molinspiration.com/cgi-bin/properties) and/or Mcule (mcule.com, Palo Alto California USA). For use of Mcule, the investigator may input the SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System) designation of the compound and obtain an extensive list of molecular properties. The visualization of the

molecular structures can be done by use ACD ChemSketch Modeling v. 12.01 (Advanced Chemistry Development, 110 Yonge Street, Toronto Ontario, M5C 1T4 Canada). EPI Suite can also be utilized for molecular properties determination (US EPA Estimation Programs Interface v. 1.40, 2012, epa.com).^[5]

Statistical Analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis

For the determination of multiple regression analysis as well as numerical statistics (i.e. 95% confidence interval, median, mean, standard deviation), was accomplished utilizing InStat Statistical Analysis Package v. 3.06 2003 (copyright 1992-2003 GraphPad Software, www.graphpad.com).

Pattern recognition analysis for Discriminant Analysis and following principal component analysis (PCA) for Convex Hulls and 95% ellipsis, was accomplished utilizing PAST version 2.15 (copyright Oyvind Hammer, D.A.T. Harper, 1999-2012).^[6]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seven Effective Antimicrobial Agents and Multiple Regression Analysis

The survival rate following infection with *Naegleria fowleri* is extremely low at only 2 percent.^[2] Rapid diagnosis and administration of effective antimicrobials is vital for survival.^[2] Due to the very high fatality rate, rapidity of illness, and difficulty of diagnosis, the investigation via clinical trials is profoundly challenging and unlikely. Treatment of this infection is largely guided by past experience, whether it being success or failure.^[2] Thus far, it is generally accepted that the following agents have been demonstrated to have efficacy and levels of effectiveness for the clinical treatment of *N. fowleri* infection: Amphotericin B, miltefosine, fluconazole voriconazole, azithromycin, rifampin, and posaconazole.^[1,2,3] The molecular properties of these seven agents are presented in Table 1 (units for polar surface area are Angstroms², or Å²)

Table 1: Seven Effective Antimicrobials and Molecular Properties.

Antimicrobial	Mass	Log P	Polar Surface Area (Å ²)	H-Bond Acceptors	H-Bond Donors	Number of Atoms	Refractivity	Violations Rule of 5
Amphotericin B	924.08	1.41	319.61	18	12	138	239.06	3
Miltefosine	407.57	6.75	68.4	4	0	73	115.9	1
Fluconazole	306.27	0.74	81.65	9	1	34	70.71	0
Voriconazole	349.31	2.18	76.72	9	1	39	81.19	0
Azithromycin	748.98	1.84	180.08	14	5	124	200.78	2
Rifampin	822.94	4.35	220.15	16	6	117	234.22	3
Posaconazole	700.78	4.70	115.7	14	1	93	194.12	2

Examining the molecular properties in Table 1 will lend insight into similarities among these seven antimicrobials which have been demonstrated to be effective for successful application in the clinical treatment of *N. fowleri* infection.^[1,2,3] Clinical studies to measure the medical response to *N. fowleri* treatment is profoundly

difficult to implement due to the rapidity and extreme lethal outcome of the infection.^[1] The summation of the clinical response to *N. fowleri* infection, is assimilated from what few successful clinical treatment outcomes have been recorded.^[1] Drug-likeness for these seven antimicrobials is estimated under the Rule of 5 criteria

(see Table 1). The Rule of 5 states that agents that violate two or more of the following criteria will have poor oral absorption or permeability: 1) Molecular weight less than 500 daltons; 2) Number of hydrogen bond donors less than or equal to 5; 3) Number of hydrogen bond acceptors less than or equal to 10; 4) A value of Log P less than or equal to 5.^[7] Applying the Rule of 5 screening method; azithromycin, rifampin, and posaconazole will have unfavorable drug-likeness and poor permeability or oral absorption.

Descriptive statistics of the numerical molecular properties shown in Table 1, are presented in Table 2. Observing the numerical values of molecular properties for mean, median, standard deviation, and 95%

confidence interval reveals an interesting range in some important drug-likeness properties. Noticeably, the molecular masses have a standard deviation of 2500, and a broad 95% confidence interval from 378.05 to 839.08 (plausible range of values for the true population parameter of mean, with a 95% confidence level).^[6] Similarly, for Log P, polar surface area, and number of atoms have a broad 95% confidence interval of 1.163 to 5.15, 65.29 A² to 238.23 A², and 50 to 126, respectively.

Nevertheless, this broad numerical range of several important drug-likeness properties does not cancel the vital necessity of focusing on rationally selected antimicrobials to halt the highly lethal *N. fowleri* infection.^[1]

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Seven Effective Antimicrobials.

Statistic	Mass	Log P	Polar Surface Area (A ²)	H-Bond Acceptor	H-Bond Donors	Number of Atoms	Refractivity	Violations of Rule of 5
Mean	608.56	3.13	151.76	12	4	88	162.28	2
Standard Deviation	2.5x10 ²	2.2	93	4.9	4.3	41	72	1
Median	700.78	2.18	115.70	14	1.0	93	194.12	2
95% Confidence Interval	378.05-839.08	1.13-5.15	65.29-238.23	7.50-16.5	0-7.70	50-126	96.15-228.42	0-3

Use of multiple regression analysis achieves multiple important objectives such as: 1) Prediction of a dependent variable value; 2) Determine the statistical significance of the independent variables to the dependent variable; 3) Explain interaction of independent variable with other independent variables; 4) Enable causal inference of relationships of all variables.^[4,8] Results of multiple regression analysis utilizing five molecular properties found in Table 1 for all seven effective and utilized antimicrobials in the treatment of *N. fowleri* infection produced the model below. Mass is the dependent variable and molecular properties are independent variables. This model is an excellent fit to the multivariate data set (see Table 1), where 99.96 percent of the variance within the data set is represented by the model (R² = 0.9996). Contribution to the model from each of the independent variables as well as the constant, were quite small, as none of these were determined to be a significant contributor to the overall model (e.g. this includes all independent variables and the constant, where all independent variables showed P>.05).

$$\text{Mass} = -36.072 + (21.786)(\text{Log P}) - (0.7366)(\text{Polar Surface Area}) + (28.750)(\text{H-bond acceptor}) + (17.253)(\text{H-bond donors}) + (3.160)(\text{Number of atoms})$$

Utilizing the molecular properties of the seven known effective antimicrobial agents in the treatment of *N. fowleri* infections (see Table 1 and Table 2), it will be possible to quickly determine which additional

pharmaceuticals have the potential to reduce or terminate *N. fowleri* infection. Next, is the discussion of five potentially effective antimicrobials, in which there is comparison of drug-likeness properties and statistical evaluation using pattern recognition methods.

Five Agents With Drug-likeness Properties For Effective Growth Inhibition of *Naegleria fowleri* Five antimicrobial agents are introduced here, that show molecular properties similar to the seven agents that have previously been shown to be effective in terminating *N. fowleri* infection.^[1,2,3] These antimicrobials are: ergosterol (antifungal), tioconazole (antifungal), methicillin (antibiotic), piperacillin (antibiotic), and aztroenam (antibiotic). The molecular properties of which are shown in Table 3, for comparison individually to the seven successful antimicrobials shown in Table 1.

Table 3: Molecular Properties of Five Potential Antimicrobials.

Antimicrobial	Mass	Log P	Polar Surface Area (Å ²)	H-Bond Acceptors	H-Bond Donors	Number of Atoms	Refractivity	Violations of Rule of 5
Ergosterol (antifungal)	396.65	7.33	20.23	1	1	73	127.47	1
Tioconazole (antifungal)	387.71	5.86	55.29	3	0	36	96.07	1
Methicillin (antibiotic)	380.41	1.28	130.47	8	2	46	98.26	0
Piperacillin (antibiotic)	517.56	0.36	181.73	12	3	63	138.8	2
Aztroenam (antibiotic)	435.44	0.81	238.20	13	4	45	99.76	5

Looking at the 95% confidence interval for mass (see Table 2), it is readily seen by inspection that all masses of the five potential antimicrobials (see Table 3), fall within that interval. Likewise, for H-bond donors property, the five potential antimicrobials (see Table 3) fall within the 95% confidence interval of the number of H-bond donors for the seven effective agents (see Table 2). In respect to properties of Log P, polar surface area, H-bond acceptors, number of atoms, refractivity, and violations of Rule of 5 (see Table 3); of the five potential antimicrobials that are within the 95% confidence interval (Table 2): for Log P are methicillin; for polar surface area are methicillin, piperacillin, aztroenam; for

H-bond acceptors are methicillin, piperacillin, aztroenam; for number of atoms are ergosterol, piperacillin; for refractivity are ergosterol, methicillin, piperacillin, aztroenam; and for Rule of 5 are ergosterol, tioconazole, methicillin, piperacillin, respectively. However, for cases where the property values fall outside the 95% confidence interval, the actual numerical values of these properties are not distant from those found with the seven agents effective for clinical treatment of *N. fowleri* infection. At this juncture, pattern recognition methods will be greatly useful in further discernment of the potential of agents in Table 3.

Figure 1: Following Principal Components Analysis, the 95% ellipses for the seven effective antimicrobials (agents 1 to 7 in numerical order descending, see Table 1) contains the 95% ellipses for the five potential antimicrobials (agents 8 to 12 in numerical order descending, see Table 3).

Principal components analysis (PCA) is a pattern recognition method utilized to reduce the dimensionality of a large multivariate data set into a smaller and easier to interpret set of variables referred to as principal components.^[6] Examination by use of PCA reveals the underlying relationships of the original data set.^[4,8] Combining property values of Table 1 (seven effective agents) with property values of Table 3 (five potential effective agents) and analysis by use of PCA with 95% ellipses produced the overlapping 95% ellipses encompassing all 12 antimicrobials (see Figure 1).

These two overlapping ellipses reveals the overall congruence of molecular properties for both sets of agents and in addition, the anticipated success of the five potential antimicrobials (Table 3) to terminate or reduce *N. fowleri* infection. By inspection and use of statistical analysis, other agents having similar drug-likeness properties, can be identified to be additional agents that will along with the seven historically successful agents, be effective for the treatment of *N. fowleri* infection. As a result, the quantity of useful antimicrobial agents is expanded, and provide advantage to the clinicians. Infections of *N. fowleri* require great speed in treatment and diagnosis. Expanding the number of effective antimicrobials will be advantageous in the event there be

only a limited stock of antimicrobials or zero record of historically effective antimicrobials.

Convex Hulls are a highly versatile instrument of pattern recognition that is applied for many purposes.^[9,10] The many applications of Convex Hull include the following: 1) Evaluate and compare different data sets to each other; 2) Detect outliers; 3) Measure central tendencies of data; 4) Define data boundaries and clusters; 5) Define classification of a set of points; and 6) Optimize data.^[9,10] In general terms, the use of Convex Hull is a powerful tool to understand boundaries, dispersion, and inter-relationships within discrete data sets and between data sets.^[9,10]

Shown in Figure 2 are a very strong overlap of Convex Hull for the seven effective and applied antimicrobial agents for clinical treatment (agents 1 to 7, see Table 1 in descending numerical order) and Convex Hull for the five potential antimicrobial agents (agents 8 to 12, see Table 3 in descending numerical order). There is a very strong overlap of the five potential agents with the seven used and effective clinical agents. These Convex Hull results are the outcome following Principal Components Analysis of the combined data sets of Table 1 and Table 3.

Figure 2: Strong overlap of Convex Hull for seven effective and applied antimicrobial agents for clinical treatment (agents 1 to 7 in numerical order descending, see Table 1), Convex Hull for the five potential antimicrobial agents (agents 8 to 12 in numerical order descending, see Table 3). There is a strong overlap of five potential agents with the seven used and effective clinical agents. Results outcome from Principal Components Analysis of Table 1 and Table 3 combined.

Important drug-likeness properties for seven effective agents have been determined, and with descriptive statistics, followed with pattern recognition methods to identify congruent similarities with five additional agents that are predicted to effectively terminate or reduce infection by *N. fowleri*.

Next, the case of rejecting antimicrobial agents that have substantially too large molecular mass, polar surface area, H-bond acceptors, number of atoms, and refractivity, will be presented. Pattern recognition

analysis is applied, along with simple numerical inspection for identifying properties outside the limits set by the seven successful effective antimicrobials (see Table 2).

Three Antimicrobials Not Suitable For Clinical Treatment of *Naegleria fowleri* Infection

Shown in Table 4 are the corresponding drug-likeness properties for three example antimicrobials that are not anticipated to effectively eliminate or reduce *N. fowleri* infection. They are ramoplanin, daptomycin, and

fidaxomicin (see Table 4). Close examination of the drug-likeness properties presented will explain.

Simple comparison of numerical values of properties in Table 4 to those of the seven effective agents in Table 1 (and with descriptive statistics in Table 2), clearly

indicates that Table 4 properties are substantially too large in molecular mass, polar surface area, H-bond acceptors, number of atoms, and refractivity. Previous studies have shown that these drug-likeness properties are vital for estimating drug permeability, drug absorption, and drug bioavailability.^[7]

Table 4: Three Antimicrobials Not Suitable for Clinical Treatment of *N. fowleri* Infection.

Antimicrobial	Mass	Log P	Polar Surface Area (Å ²)	H-Bond Acceptors	H-Bond Donors	Number of Atoms	Refractivity	Violations Rule of 5
Ramoplanin antibiotic	2554.06	1.17	999.59	61	36	335	690.32	3
Daptomycin antibiotic	1620.67	0.88	702.02	43	39	216	433.86	3
Fidaxomicin antibiotic	1058.03	6.23	266.66	18	7	146	268.58	4

Discriminant Analysis and Convex Hull are pattern recognition methods that will clearly show the three agents in Table 4 should not be suitable for effective treatment of *N. fowleri* infection. Discriminant Analysis, a pattern recognition methodology, is used to: 1) Classify observations as well as assign new observations to pre-determined groups utilizing predictor variables; 2) Determine group differences using known variables; and 3) Identify the key predictor variable (i.e. which variables are optimum for group differentiation).^[11]

Discriminant Analysis of the multivariate data set obtained by combining both Table 1 (seven effective

agents) and Table 4 (agents not suitable for treatment), was accomplished utilizing PAST version 2.15 (copyright Oyvind Hammer, D.A.T. Harper, 1999-2012).^[6] Results are shown in Table 5, which clearly differentiates the seven effective antimicrobials (Group 1 in Table 5) from the three not suitable antimicrobials (Group 2 in Table 5). These two groups were distinguished, separated, and found to be distinct after analysis of their molecular properties by Discriminant Analysis (see Table 1 and Table 4).

Table 5: Discriminant Analysis of Seven Effective and Three Not Suitable Antimicrobials.

Antimicrobials	Group Assignment Discriminant Analysis
Amphotericin B	1
Miltefosine	1
Fluconazole	1
Voriconazole	1
Azithromycin	1
Rifampin	1
Posaconazole	1
Ramoplanin antibiotic	2
Daptomycin antibiotic	2
Fidaxomicin antibiotic	2

In addition, Convex Hull pattern recognition method showed that the seven effective agents are distinct and differentiated from the three not suitable agents, based on the drug-likeness molecular properties presented in Table 1 and Table 4. In Figure 3, is shown that the Convex Hull for these two groups do not overlap and are significantly separated within the two-way graph of Component 1 versus Component 2. Again, pattern recognition analysis is able to differentiate the seven successful and effective agents for treating *N. fowleri* infection, from agents having molecular properties not consistent, numerically distinct, and distant from those of

the seven effective agents (Table 1).

Therefore, statistical analysis of properties and application of pattern recognition methods should successfully identify effective agents and differentiate them from not suitable agents (based on the molecular properties). The ability to identify antimicrobial agents having molecular properties not congruent and distant from the seven clinically proven agents will be very helpful and gainful for accelerating the clinical treatment for this highly lethal amoebic infection.

Figure 3: Non-overlap of Convex Hulls for the seven effective antimicrobial agents for treatment of *N. fowleri* infection (agents 1 to 7, see Table 1, Table 2) and the not suitable agents for clinical treatment of *N. fowleri* infection (agents 8, 9, 10, see Table 4). Non-overlap clearly shows that two groups are not similar in Convex Hull analysis and the two groups are clearly differentiated and distinct by molecular properties. Results obtained following Principal Components Analysis.

CONCLUSION

Infection by *Naegleria fowleri* is highly lethal and has a very low survival rate. Rapid diagnosis and treatment is vital for even the possibility of survival. This study has introduced the seven known effective agents: Amphotericin B, miltefosine, fluconazole voriconazole, azithromycin, rifampin, and posaconazole.^[1,2,3] Their drug-likeness molecular properties have been determined and presented to compare to the molecular properties of five potentially effective antimicrobials (ergosterol (antifungal), tioconazole (antifungal), methicillin (antibiotic), piperacillin (antibiotic), and aztroenam (antibiotic)); in addition to three agents having substantially different properties and therefore anticipated not to be suitable for clinical use (ramoplanin, daptomycin, and fidaxomicin). This study has shown that determination of the descriptive statistics of the drug-likeness properties can itself be utilized to evaluate additional antimicrobials for potential success in the clinical treatment of *Naegleria fowleri* infection. In addition, pattern recognition methods such as Convex Hull, 95% ellipses, and Discriminant Analysis can effectuate the discernment of antimicrobials potentially successful in terminating or reducing *Naegleria fowleri* infection, from those antimicrobials not suitable for treatment by way of their molecular properties. This approach may expand the library of effective antimicrobials for life-saving application in the clinical treatment of the dangerous and highly lethal PAM condition from *Naegleria fowleri* infection.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was completed at the University of Nebraska at Omaha, College of Arts & Sciences, Chemistry Department, Durham Science Center, 6001 Dodge Street, Omaha NE 68114 USA.

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